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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****EVALUATION OF AHVAZ JUNDISHAPUR UNIVERSITY OF
MEDICAL SCIENCES RANKING IN IRAN, MIDDLE EAST
AND NEIGHBORING COUNTRIES IN 2016, A
WEBOMETRICS ANALYSIS****Zahra Khoram¹, Amir Jamshidnezhad*², Nazanin Tamoradi¹**¹Student Research committee, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences, Iran²Department of Medical Informatics, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences,
Iran**Abstract:**

University websites are of great importance to show the scientific activities of academic institutions. Qualitative and quantitative promotion of these websites, enhances the chance of recovery and visibility of medical universities in the cyber world. Ranking of Webometrics represents the degree of annual scientific activities appeared in universities website. In this study, four indicators including Size, Visibility, Richfiles and Google scholars indexing as the main indicators of Webometrics were analyzed in the Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences website. Moreover, it was evaluated in comparison with websites of other top medical universities in Iran, middle east and Iran neighboring countries. The results showed that in terms of Webometrics ranking, Lomonosov Moscow State University of Russia, King of Saudi Arabia, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, and Shahid Beheshti of Tehran were ranked first to fifth respectively. Evaluation of Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences based on the indicators showed that this site has not been successful in most of these indicators. The information provided on the web pages was not attractive at the international level. Moreover, weakness of the site in terms of Search Engine Optimization (SEO), English language of the content as well as few number of English web pages and backlinks for the university website were identified.

Keywords: Webometrics, Ranking of websites, Search engines, University visibility, Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences

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INTRODUCTION:

Increased number of universities and higher educations in recent years, has brought competition among universities for student recruitment, research projects, attracting national and international funds as well as exchange of professors and students. Therefore, a reference for evaluation and ranking of universities may help academic institutions to have the necessary information for enhancing their performances. Accordingly, in recent years, various systems are designed and executed for ranking of universities. [1]

Given the importance of student recruitment and funding, universities seek to improve their ranking in the educational systems. Today, websites are of great importance in dissemination of information in all areas of knowledge. University websites are applied as a communication tool with diverse aims from introducing a university or college, to recruit students, provide educational resources, access to electronic journals and etc. [2], [3], [4], Consequently, university websites have an important role for enhancing the quality and quantity of academic purposes with raises the chance of visibility in the virtual world.

Studies show that the web is becoming a means of communication to disseminate the scientific and research achievements obtained in university and research centers. [4] To assess the impact of scientific websites on audiences, a method called Webometrics is used. [2]

Webometrics is a field of science which deals with quantitative analysis of the nature and properties of web using methods of information measurement. In this science the analysis of web pages is carried out through calculation and analysis of their inner and external links. [5-6]

University Ranking is referred to the recognizing scientific and research status of universities, creating a fair competitive environment, motivation and progress and determining the ideal of higher education as well as finding weakness of academic centers in order to fix their lacks. [1]

Improving the status of websites in accordance with the method of Webometrics means better, more and faster visibility of website by the search engine robots and more visibility of academic activities through the Web and ultimately, enhancing the academic and education aims in the current competitive environment. [4]

University ranking systems are created since 1865. Today, there are more than 25 national and the international systems of university rankings in the world. Times Higher Education Supplement in England as the oldest ranking system, Shanghai,

Webometrics ranking of the Spain Cybermetric Research Lab, and finally Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC) are the most important of ranking methods. [1]

Cybermetric Lab which is a research project related to National Research Council of Spain, has started the Webometrics since 2004.

Webometrics is a method for universities and scientific centers web ranking which provided by Cybermetric Lab. Webometrics analyzes 8000 world universities twice a year in January and September according to information of universities web. Webometrics is created to show the attention of institutions to cyber publishing. The purpose of this ranking is to motivate institutions and researchers to participate in the web to promote the contents of the web, webpages publishing, electronic access to scientific publications and so on.

Universities with high education quality may not gain their expected and qualified ranking in these types of rankings, due to unwillingness to cyber publishing policy. However, in this method, high education institutions achieve a better status by publishing their scientific achievements on the internet. In this ranking system, analysis unit is the Website of university or institution. Therefore, to promote the Webometrics ranking, paying attention to the four ranking factors in universities website are important. [2] Calculated indicators are four criteria including:

- Size of webpages
- Visibility of website
- Rich files
- The number of articles profiled in Google scholar

Aminpoor and Atraj used the Webometrics method to evaluate the medical universities in Iran. They showed that the studied universities were not much presence on the web, probably due to the low number of English web pages as well as youngness of universities websites. [3] They also found that defect in the structure and content of medical universities website is the most important reason in low Webometrics ranking. Weakness in the websites design, few updated pages in English, lack of comprehensive map and internal search engine, limitation in access to information resources through Websites and low rate of electronic publishing are some of the reasons for low ranking of medical universities in the Webometrics. [6] Moreover, a study by Jashankar and Ramesh Babu showed that sites with greater number of web pages and external links as well as more external web impact, have earned a higher rating. [7]

Wafa el-Houri et al. have done a study in Beirut through which designed an automated ranking system based on Webometrics system. Results of the study, can be a guide for universities to work on their weaknesses in order to improve their ranking index, and in addition to this system, it offers a list of changes needed to any website that helps achieve a higher ranking. [10]

Webometrics performance of universities in Russia and Poland has been analyzed in a study by Novak during 2005 to 2009. The results showed that the general performance of these universities is weak in terms of Webometrics ranking; among them the state University of Moscow gained the first in ranking. [12]

Samir Kumar et al. in an analytical study using Yahoo, investigated Indian University websites. They showed that Indian universities has a significant progress in the development of universities websites. Delhi University has earned the first place in the Webometrics ranking. [11]

Rahimi in a study based on Webometrics, showed that the websites of Isfahan University of Medical sciences in term of scientific evidence, Medical University of Tehran in terms of size, visibility and traffic, and Shiraz University of Medical Sciences in terms of design are in the first place; totally Universities of Medical Sciences of Tehran, Isfahan, and Shiraz ranked first to third respectively, from the entire Web indices among the Universities of Medical Sciences of the country.[8]

Rouyayi found that Websites of Turkey University's (Ankara) based on the studied indices in this paper, has the highest participation among 10 top Websites of studied universities; it also showed the underrepresentation of Iranian universities among top universities of Islamic countries in the web. [9]

In the present study, the Websites of the Medical University of type 1 of Ahvaz and Iran's Universities

of Medical Sciences of type 1, are investigated and analyzed using 4 Webometrics indices by Google, Yahoo and Bing search engines, and also top universities of Middle East and the countries neighboring Iran are also analyzed with the same method and compared with Iran's type one universities. In this study, instead of using Majestic Seo reference that is used in Webometrics, Google and Yahoo references are also used. In addition to that, the details of rankings of universities' Websites in this study are extracted so that the strengths and weaknesses of Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences could be more effectively shown in comparison with the other universities.

As a result, this study aimed to determine the strengths and weaknesses of the University of Ahvaz so as to more clarify its status of science and research in the country, and its presence in the World Wide Web.

METHODOLOGY:

The study population consists of the information retrieved from Websites of 8 type 1 Iran universities of medical sciences and top universities in the Middle East and Iran neighbor countries. To access the portals of type 1 Iran Universities, the official site of Ministry of Health Sciences was used in 2016. Also, to compare the Webometrics ranking of Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences with the universities in the Middle east and Iran neighbors, Websites of top universities were analyzed. To find the first ranks of Medical universities in Iran neighbor countries and the Middle East, the Islamic world ranking and Times ranking system were used. As a result, all the websites of top universities in the Middle East and Iran neighbor countries in this study were analyzed and compared with each other in terms of Webometrics. Studied Universities are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of Evaluated Universities

Rank	Domain	country	Name
1	Tums.ac.ir	Iran	Tehran
2	Sums.ac.ir	Iran	Shiraz
3	mui.ac.ir	Iran	Esfahan
4	mums.ac.ir	Iran	Mashhad
5	sbm.ac.ir	Iran	Shahid beheshti
6	tbzmed.ac.ir	Iran	Tabriz
7	ajums.ac.ir	Iran	Ahvaz
8	kmu.ac.ir	Iran	Kerman
9	Damascus university.edu.sy	Syria	Damascus
10	cu.edu.eg	Egypt	Cairo
11	uobaghdad.edu.iq	Iraq	Baghdad
12	ju.edu.jo	Jordan	Jordan
13	aub.edu.lb	Lebanon	American university of beirut
14	squ.edu.om	Oman	Sultan Qaboos
15	aku.edu	Pakistan	Aga Khan
16	hamad.qa	Qatar	Hamad medical corporation
17	ksu.edu.sa	Saudi Arabia	King saud
18	uofk.edu	sudan	Khartoum
19	istanbul.edu.tr	Turkey	Istanbul
20	uaeu.ac.ae	United Arab Emirate	United Arab Emirate
21	academy.uz	Uzbek	Fanlar
22	su.edu.ye	Yamen	Sana'a
23	uot.edu.ly	Libya	Tripoli
24	ku.edu.kw	Kuwait	Kuwait
25	ysu.am	Armenia	Yerevan state
26	du.ac.in	India	Delhi
27	msu.ru	Russia	Lomonosov Moscow State

This research was conducted using the Webometrics method. The presence and impact of information available on the web, visibility, access to content-based files, and the number of websites profiled articles were evaluated directly. Moreover, the status of websites was identified in Google, Yahoo, and Bing search engines. In this study, four indices were used that briefly include: number of pages (S), visibility V, rich files R, and the number of profiled articles of Google Scholar.

With the identification of any of the above ranking indices, the Websites ranking of each university can be measured on the basis of the following formula:

$$I = 2Rs + 4Rv + Rr + RG.S$$

I = Total score

R = Relative Position

Scholar G.S : Google , r : rich file, v : visibility
s : size

Data retrieving of this research was conducted in spring and summer, 2016.

FINDINGS:

The population of this study consists of Iran type 1 Universities of Medical Sciences and universities of the Middle East and Iran neighboring countries. In Webometrics ranking, the numbers of web pages, impact and visibility, the number of files and the number of indexed articles on Google Scholar have been used for evaluating and ranking. In this study, after obtaining the scores of the Websites based on each of the indicators listed, final ranking was identified.

Table2: University ranks based on size on Google, yahoo, Bing

Domain	Name	Google	Yahoo	Bing	Average	Rank
Tums.ac.ir	Tehran	387,000	106,000	105,000	199,333	5
Sums.ac.ir	Shiraz	184,000	91,700	92,900	122,867	10
mui.ac.ir	Esfahan	188,000	77,200	76,900	114,033	12
mums.ac.ir	Mashhad	231,000	70,800	69,800	123,867	9
sbmu.ac.ir	Shahid beheshti	294,000	57,000	56,800	135,933	8
tbzmed.ac.ir	Tabriz	259,000	81,900	80,600	140,500	7
ajums.ac.ir	Ahvaz	154,000	17,600	17,500	63,033	17
kmu.ac.ir	Kerman	750,000	15,800	15,800	390,800	3
Damascus university.edu.sy	Damascus	47,400	9,500	9,600	22,167	22
cu.edu.eg	Cairo	161,000	36,500	37,100	78,200	14
uobaghdad.edu.iq	Baghdad	119,000	14,800	15,000	49,600	18
ju.edu.jo	Jordan	333,000	44,200	44,600	140,600	6
aub.edu.lb	American university of beirut	107,000	42,300	42,600	63,967	16
squ.edu.om	Sultan Qaboos	105,000	7,990	8,060	40,350	19
aku.edu	Aga Khan	16,300	17,900	18,000	17,400	23
hamad.qa	Hamad medical corporation	9,960	12,100	12,200	11,420	24
ksu.edu.sa	King saud	422,000	592,000	594,000	536,000	2
uofk.edu	Khartoum	321,000	15,500	15,700	117,400	11
istanbul.edu.tr	Istanbul	369,000	199,000	201,000	256,333	4
uaeu.ac.ae	United Arab Emirate	46,500	20,600	20,900	29,333	20
academy.uz	Fanlar	2,720	1,390	1,410	1,840	26
su.edu.ye	Sana'a	491	45	981	506	27
uot.edu.ly	Tripoli	2,350	2,430	2,470	2,417	25
ku.edu.kw	Kuwait	59,100	5,300	5,370	23,257	21
ysu.am	Yerevan state	314,000	5,040	5,100	108,047	13
du.ac.in	Delhi	115,000	58,100	58,300	77,133	15
msu.ru	Lomonosov Moscow State	439,000	685,000	685,000	603,000	1

By examining Table 2 and comparing the average number of pages obtained from the three search engines Google, Yahoo, Bing, we can conclude that Lomonosov Moscow State University with the highest mean, is in the first place and Yemen

University with the lowest mean is in 27th place. Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences in google, yahoo, and Bing, ranked 15th, 18th, and 17th respectively among 27 universities.

Table 3 : External links obtained from the majestic SEO

Domain	Name	Majestic seo	Rank
Tums.ac.ir	Tehran	1,509,191	5
Sums.ac.ir	Shiraz	22,228,122	1
mui.ac.ir	Esfahan	249,461	14
mums.ac.ir	Mashhad	271,635	13
sbmu.ac.ir	Shahid beheshti	2,514,093	3
tbzmed.ac.ir	Tabriz	597,356	9
ajums.ac.ir	Ahvaz	62,918	21
kmu.ac.ir	Kerman	78,711	18
Damascus university.edu.sy	Damascus	34,652	24
cu.edu.eg	Cairo	1,577,646	4
uobaghdad.edu.iq	Baghdad	130,124	15
ju.edu.jo	Jordan	652,346	8
aub.edu.lb	American university of beirut	299,181	12
squ.edu.om	Sultan Qaboos	37,671	23
aku.edu	Aga Khan	85,876	17
hamad.qa	Hamad medical corporation	44,590	22
ksu.edu.sa	King saud	934,301	6
uofk.edu	Khartoum	309,329	11
istanbul.edu.tv	Istanbul	851,396	7
uaeu.ac.ae	United Arab Emirate	64,921	20
academy.uz	Fanlar	74,835	19
su.edu.ye	Sana'a	812	27
uot.edu.ly	Tripoli	18,908	27
ku.edu.kw	Kuwait	117,923	16
ysu.am	Yerevan state	29,515	25
du.ac.in	Delhi	403,073	10
msu.ru	Lomonosov Moscow State	3,315,786	2

Examining Table 3 and comparing external links obtained from the majestic seo site show that the University of Shiraz, with the most links is in the first place, and the Yemen University with the lowest

links is in 27th place. Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences is in 21th place, which indicates its weakness in terms of loading that site in search engines, compared with other universities.

Table 4: Size of rich files in the universities' websites

Domain	Name	PDF	DOC	XLS	XLM	PPT	Total number of rich files	Rank
Tums.ac.ir	Tehran	121,000	3,330	11,400	59,600	2,690	198,020	2
Sums.ac.ir	Shiraz	23,600	2,960	5	1	1,050	27,616	17
mui.ac.ir	Esfahan	55,800	4,410	174	28,300	8	88,692	8
mums.ac.ir	Mashhad	74,100	7,250	404	14,400	2,580	98,734	6
sbmu.ac.ir	Shahid beheshti	90,000	3,040	271	8	1,430	94,749	7
tbzmed.ac.ir	Tabriz	44,800	3,390	7	2	1,400	49,599	13
ajums.ac.ir	Ahvaz	30,000	17,900	318	11,200	759	60,177	11
kmua.ac.ir	Kerman	18,800	9	6	1	6	18,822	19
Damascus university.edu.sy	Damascus	26,700	1,940	446	1	1,640	30,727	16
cu.edu.eg	Cairo	55,500	2,980	389	5	1,840	60,714	10
uobaghdad.edu.iq	Baghdad	28,900	3,720	9	1	1,100	33,730	15
ju.edu.jo	Jordan	130,000	16,200	449	1	2,450	149,100	4
aub.edu.lb	American university of Beirut	36,800	4,000	821	2	1,180	42,803	14
squ.edu.om	Sultan Qaboos	6,860	3,120	64	2,920	165	13,129	21
aku.edu	Aga Khan	3,740	163	6	103	7	4,019	23
hamad.qa	Hamad medical corporation	1,480	9	4	5	2	1,500	24
ksu.edu.sa	King saud	350,000	150,000	14,000	15	101,000	615,015	1
uofk.edu	Khartoum	64,000	724	36	1	693	65,454	9
istanbul.edu.tr	Istanbul	83,300	79,400	2,010	4	3,060	120,774	5
uaeu.ac.ae	United Arab Emirate	6,200	557	3	1	311	7,072	22
academy.uz	Fanlar	62	29	0	2	0	93	25
su.edu.ye	Sana'a	3	0	0	0	0	3	27
uot.edu.ly	Tripoli	6	5	2	1	1	15	26
ku.edu.kw	Kuwait	13,300	228	30	1	69	13,628	20
ysu.am	Yerevan state	17,300	2,050	23	2	692	20,067	18
du.ac.in	Delhi	44,300	11,700	9	1	1,030	57,040	12
msu.ru	Lomonosov Moscow State	156,000	21,700	4,170	35	3,810	185,715	3

Table 4 shows that in terms of the number of rich files, the website of King Saud University is in the first place (formats of PDF, DOC, PPT, XLM, XLS related to scientific evidence and activities published by the University) and the last place in this regard belongs to Yemen University with 3 rich files. Place of Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences in PPT,

XLM, XLS, DOC, PDF, files is 18, 4, 11, 5, 16 respectively, and the overall rating of this site in terms of rich files is 12.

By comparing the obtained data according to Table 4, the PDF format was the most used format in the websites and XLS is the least used one.

Table 5: Number of articles indexed in the Google scholar

Domain	Name	Google scholar	Rank
Tums.ac.ir	Tehran	14,200	2
Sums.ac.ir	Shiraz	1,640	15
mui.ac.ir	Esfahan	3,800	9
mums.ac.ir	Mashhad	6,090	6
sbmu.ac.ir	Shahid beheshti	6,220	5
tbzmed.ac.ir	Tabriz	2,450	11
ajums.ac.ir	Ahvaz	700	17
kmu.ac.ir	Kerman	1,710	14
Damascus university.edu.sy	Damascus	165	21
cu.edu.eg	Cairo	14,900	1
uobaghdad.edu.iq	Baghdad	2,100	13
ju.edu.jo	Jordan	4,790	8
aub.edu.lb	American university of beirut	4,940	7
squ.edu.om	Sultan Qaboos	8	24
aku.edu	Aga Khan	2,360	12
hamad.qa	Hamad medical corporation	13	23
ksu.edu.sa	King saud	10,300	3
uofk.edu	Khartoum	7,420	4
istanbul.edu.tr	Istanbul	255	20
uaeu.ac.ae	United Arab Emirate	1,220	16
academy.uz	Fanlar	0	25
su.edu.ye	Sana'a	0	26
uot.edu.ly	Tripoli	0	27
ku.edu.kw	Kuwait	147	22
ysu.am	Yerevan state	352	18
du.ac.in	Delhi	329	19
msu.ru	Lomonosov Moscow State	2,990	10

According to Table 5, the Egyptian University with 14,900 indexed papers in Google Scholar is in first place and Universities of Uzbekistan, Yemen and Libya, all are in the last place due to the lack of any article, and Ahvaz University is also in the 17th place. Table 6 shows the overall ranking of websites based yielded on the basis of indices of the number of pages, visibility, rich files, and the number of articles that using the following formula:

$$I = 2R_s + 4R_v + R_r + R_{G.s}$$

According to this table, Russia University is in the first place and Yemen University is in the 27th place. Ahvaz University were also ranked 17th.

According to the Figure 1, among 8 Iran Universities of Medical Sciences, Tehran University of Medical Sciences is in first place and Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences is in 8th place among type 1 universities of medical sciences in Iran.

Table 6 : Total Rank

Rank	name	Domain	Rs	Rv	Rr	RG.s	Rank
1	Lomonosov Moscow State	Msu.ru	2	2	4	11	27
2	Saudi Arabia	Ksu.edu.sa	3	6	2	3	35
3	Tehran	Tums.ac.ir	6	5	3	2	37
4	Shahid beheshti	Sbmu.ac.ir	9	3	8	5	43
5	Cairo	Cu.edu.eg	15	4	11	1	58
6	Shiraz	Sums.ac.ir	11	1	18	16	60
7	Jordan	Ju.edu.jo	7	9	5	8	63
8	Istanbul	Istanbul.edu.tr	5	8	6	21	69
9	Tabriz	Tbzmed.ac.ir	8	10	14	12	82
10	Khartoum	Uofk.edu	13	12	10	4	86
11	Mashhad	Mums.ac.ir	10	14	7	6	89
12	Esfahan	Mui.ac.ir	13	15	9	10	105
13	American university of Beirut	Aub.edu.lb	17	13	15	7	108
14	Delhi	Du.ac.in	16	11	14	20	109
15	Kerman	Knu.ac.ir	4	19	20	15	119
16	Baghdad	Uobaghdad.edu.iq	19	16	16	14	132
17	Ahvaz	Ajums.ac.ir	18	22	12	18	154
18	Kuwait	Ku.edu.kw	22	17	21	23	156
19	Aga khan	Aku.edu	24	18	24	13	157
20	United Arab Emirate	Uaeu.ac.ae	21	21	23	17	166
21	Yerevan State	Ysu.am	14	26	19	19	170
22	Sultan Qaboos	Squ.edu.om	20	24	22	25	183
23	Fanlar akademiyasi	Academy.uz	27	20	26	26	186
24	Hamad medical	Hamad.qa	25	23	25	28	195
25	Damascus	Damascus university.edu.sy	23	25	17	22	205
26	Tripoli	Uot.edu.ly	26	27	27	28	215
27	Sana'a	Su.edu.ye	28	28	28	27	223

Table 7. Trend of Ahvaz Jundishapur University of Medical Sciences Rating from 2011 to 2016

Calculated I	Rich files					Visibility				Size				index year
	ppt	xml	xls	doc	pdf	average	Majestic Seo	bing	yahoo	average	bing	yahoo	google	
1100	3	2	9	305	781	1297		568	2025	7526	1750	1029	19800	2011
60177	759	11200	318	17900	30000	63033	62918	17600	17500	63033	17500	17600	1540	2016

Fig 1: Total Rank of Type 1 Universities of Medical Sciences in Iran

DISCUSSION:

One of the aims of the Webometrics system is to motivate scientific, research and universities institutions, for accurate offering and reflection of their activities on the web. [1] Today, one aspect of the success of any university, is its presence in web. Results showed that generally, among Iran's type 1 medical sciences universities, only two Tehran and Shahid Beheshti Universities were included in the 5 top universities and other universities gained middle and lower rankings which reflects their low impact on the web, the number of web pages of some of these universities is high though. According to data it could also be concluded that top universities have more external links and pages compared to other universities, which can be one of the important factors in their success. According to the research, the University of Russia ranked the best, and after that University of Saudi Arabia ranked second and the Tehran University of Medical Sciences ranked the third.

According to this study, among Iran universities, websites of University of Kerman in terms of index of page number, Shiraz University in terms of index

of external links of the Majestic Site, Tehran University in terms of indices of rich files and the number of indexed articles in Google Scholar are in the first place. Ahvaz University of Medical Sciences has a relatively poor performance in terms of Webometrics indices. The website of this university is ranked very poorly in the Majestic Site, and since the Majestic is an important index, it could be one reason for the low rating of Ahvaz University; this University had also poor performance in other indices except the doc and xlm files.

Table 7 shows the performance of Ahvaz Medical University during the last 5 years. Achieved results showed the significant growth in the last 5 years, however, the overall performance of Ahvaz Medical University in all aspects of Webometrics in comparison with other universities is weak, so it needs revision and effort of the relevant authorities of this university to increase parameters and overall rating. [4] Improving in some factors such as Google scholar can be showed in the case of increasing the number of researcher and faculty members' articles indexed in the Google scholars. In Ref. [13] a sample of indexed article was presented.

According to past research, Iran type 1 Universities of Medical Sciences, could not obtain a significant rating in Webometrics system and this can represent weakness of the websites in terms of Webometrics indices. The results of these studies indicate that websites that have used more non-English pages have typically received fewer links, thus have had less audience that this leads to less presence on the web and lowness of the impact factor in these Websites. [1-3-4-9]

Top Universities of Medical Sciences of the country also were not enough presented on the web, and also not known at the international level. Low number of English web pages and the youngness of the websites of Iran Universities, are of the major reasons for the presence of universities of Medical Sciences on web." [3]

In this study, this point is very important that in Iran, Universities of Medical Sciences, are separated from other non-health and medical fields as they are under the supervision of the Ministry of Health and Medical Education while other disciplines are under the Ministry of Science and Research. But, in the rest of the studied countries, this separation is not applied, therefore it is not unexpected that the indicators rating obtained for the websites of these universities be higher than Iranian universities.

CONCLUSION:

The results illustrated the importance of Webometrics in Iran universities in the recent years. In this paper, a descriptive study was conducted among 27 medical sciences universities from Iran, Middle East and Iran neighboring countries. The research data were collected in spring 2016; web sites of these universities were examined and analyzed according to Webometrics method.

Evaluation of Ahvaz University Medical Sciences showed that the website has not been successful in the most of the Webometrics parameters. It seems that the external link obtained by the Majestic Site, as the most important factor in Webometrics ranking, has not grown in proportion with the other indicators. Majestic site has dedicated a very small percentage of external links that could imply that the information provided in the university webpages are not globally appealing. Moreover, structural weakness of the website, Persian language of the content, few English web pages and youngness of the website are other limitations of the evaluated website.

Suggestions:

Although all rating criteria of Webometric depends on the content of websites, however, the status of website in search engines is a very important factor. Search engines are ranking instruments used by Webometric ranking for investigating the amount,

type and size of the information on the websites. Improvement of a website in search engine means better, more accurate and faster visibility of websites by search robots and therefore higher position of website in searches and ultimately more visit of the website.

Among the things that universities can do to increase their ranking in webometric include:

- Improve the structure and content of the University's website
- All the academics should contribute to increase the webometric criteria
- All the systems should be as a subdomain of the university's main domain and other subdomains should be prevented
- Teachers should enter their resume on the internet and the information should be updated, and text files of teachers should be put on the internet
- Status of university domain and IPs should be monitored so as not to be placed in any blacklist
- Interviews and technical reports provided by teachers should be placed on their personal pages on the website of university
- Production of information and creating pages by students should be encouraged
- English website must be developed alongside Farsi
- Simple designation of website along with it attractiveness, frequent updating of pages, introduction of professors, students, administrators and staff etc.

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